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Research Article

**A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF DELAYED AND EARLY
LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY IN ACUTE
CHOLECYSTITIS**¹Dr Muhammad Shoaib Aslam, ²Suman Arooj¹Continental Medical College Lahore.²Women Medical and Dental College Abbottabad**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Background: Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is considered the gold standard for the management of acute cholecystitis but controversy surrounds the timings of the surgery. Studies are available favoring both early and delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The comparison of early and delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis was the main objective of this study.

Methods: This is a part-experimental study which includes 180 patients irrespective of their age and sex when presented at department of Surgery, Services Hospital between January to December 2017. A diagnosis of acute cholecystitis was assigned randomly to early laparoscopic cholecystectomy within 24 hours of admittance or to initial conservative treatment followed by delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy, 6 to 12 weeks later.

Results: The mean time of operation was 64.32 minutes in early group and 58.24 minutes in the delayed group. The conversion rate in early group was 15.5% and delayed group was 14.4%. The mean value of postoperative stay was 1.67 days in early group and 4.38 days in delayed group. Overall mortality rate remained zero.

Conclusion: Our study concludes that early laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis is safe and offers much shorter hospital stay with quick recovery. Early laparoscopic cholecystectomy offers benefit economically as the hospital stay is shorter as compared to delayed cholecystectomy.

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INTRODUCTION:

In the developmental stages of laparoscopic cholecystectomy, acute cholecystitis was considered a contraindication for the procedure. As the experience in laparoscopic surgery has been building rapidly, it has been reported by a number of professionals that laparoscopic cholecystectomy can be used for acute cholecystitis, it is technically safe and feasible.¹⁻³ In the late 1980s early surgery for acute cholecystitis started becoming common practice.⁴ It is safe to say that laparoscopic cholecystectomy is the most common laparoscopic surgery performed globally. Traditional (initial) treatment for acute cholecystitis includes bowel rest, intravenous hydration, and correction of electrolytes abnormalities, analgesia, and includes intravenous antibiotics. This treatment comes with uncomplicated disease and patients are managed on outpatient basis and are managed after a period of 6–8 weeks.⁵

Early open cholecystectomy is now being preferred for acute cholecystitis for many reasons, to reduce morbidity, mortality and the total hospital stay.⁶ There is substantial evidence to support the superiority of early laparoscopic cholecystectomy (within 72 hours) over delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy regarding outcome control, safety and the cost of treatment.⁷ A recently published randomized study confirms this trend in patients that have been managed within 24 hours of admission. However, cholecystectomy may not always be possible within 24 hours of admission for a myriad of reasons, that's why surgery should be performed within 72 hours as recommended in several guidelines. Delayed cholecystectomy potentially increases the chances of further gallstone related complications during the waiting interval and thus additional hospital admission on recent evaluation has indicated early laparoscopic cholecystectomy to be safe option in acute cholecystitis.⁸⁻¹¹ There have only been a few studies demonstrating the feasibility of laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis. However, most surgeons prefer to delay surgery in acute phase.

The aim of this study is to compare early and delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy in the treatment of acute cholecystitis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A total of 180 patients were included in this experimental study, age and sex had been excluded. presenting through the surgical emergency and outpatient department of Services Hospital Lahore from 1st March to 1st December 2017. The following four diagnostic criteria were the bases to Diagnose

acute cholecystitis: acute abdominal pain in the upper portion and tenderness under the right costal margin, fever exceeding 37.5 C °, leukocytosis exceeding 10,500/mm, and ultra-sonographic evidence of acute cholecystitis (thickened gallbladder wall, oedematous). The laparoscopic cholecystectomy in early group was performed within 72 hours of admission. While it was performed in the delayed group after 6–8 weeks when the acute episode had subsided. Informed consent was obtained from every patient in writing. Patients with coexisting common bile duct stones, biliary pancreatitis, upper abdominal surgery or significant medical disease rendering unfit for the laparoscopic surgery were excluded. All the surgeries were performed by a single consultant to reduce the bias related to surgical hand. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy was performed using a standard 4 port technique. Modifications were used in the surgical technique in both groups which varied case to case like using gallbladder decompression, retrieval bag, placement of sub hepatic drain, and use of 5th port. Statistical analysis was performed using paired t-test and the chi square test. SPSS version 17 was used to determine the *p*-value (*p*-value less than 0.05 was considered significant). Chi-square/Fisher's exact test was applied to compare categorical data. Parameters such as conversion rates, average hospital stay, post-operative complications and operation time were assessed.

RESULTS:

During the study period, a total of 180 patients were evaluated, 90 patients in the early group and 90 patients in the delayed group. The mean operating time was 64.32 min vs. 58.24 min in the delayed group.

In the early group 14 (15.5%) of the patients underwent conversion to open surgery versus 14.4% in the delayed group. The main reasons for conversion in our study was distorted, unclear obscure Callots triangle, multiple dense adhesions all around the Callots triangle and with the surrounding structures, making dissection difficult and posing risk of bile duct injury in case of delayed cholecystectomy and difficulty in securing haemostasis.

There were no deaths in either group, the overall mortality was zero. The mean duration of post-operative analgesic requirement was 3.1±0.82 days in the earlier group and 4.2±1.24 days in the delayed group (*p*-value=0.0001). The mean postoperative hospital stay was 1.67±0.89 days in the earlier group and 4.38±1.48 days in the delayed group (*p*-value=0.0001)

Table-1. Per-operative comparison of early vs. delayed (n=180)

	Early (n=90)	Delayed (n=90)	p-value
Adhesions	24 (26.6%)	38 (42.2%)	0.028*
Required decompression	40 (44.4%)	9 (10%)	0.000*
Drain placement	30 (33.3%)	38 (42.2%)	0.22
Use of 5 th port	0 (0%)	2 (2.2%)	0.49

* statistically significant at 5% level

Table-2: Operative complications (n=180)

Intraoperative complications	Early (n=90)	Delayed (n=90)	p- value
Bile leak	6 (6.6%)	8 (8.9%)	0.78
CBD injury	0 (0%)	1 (3.3%)	0.43
Conversion rate	14 (15.5%)	13 (14.4%)	1.00
Postoperative complications			
Wound infection	8 (8.8%)	11 (12.2%)	0.62
sub hepatic collection	7 (7.7%)	10 (11.1%)	0.61
Chest infection	2 (2.2%)	1 (1.1%)	0.82
Retained CBD stones	2 (4.4%)	1 (3.3%)	0.73

DISCUSSION:

Acute cholecystitis is the most commonly encountered entity in the hepatobiliary system and cholecystectomy is the commonest surgical intervention.⁵ Several randomized clinical trials of comparisons of early laparoscopic cholecystectomy (ELC, performed within 7 days of onset of symptoms) with delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy (DLC, performed at least 6 weeks after the symptoms occurred) suggest that ELC as compared to DLC is more beneficial and has the same level of clinical safety during hospital stay. Successful laparoscopic cholecystectomy during the period of acute inflammation is associated with an early recovery and shorter hospital stay. With improvement in instrument, technique, expertise, the number of reports on laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis has increased with the conversion rates ranging from 6.5–35%.¹²⁻¹⁴

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) performed within 24 hours of admission was shown to be superior to delayed LC with regard to outcome. The authors concluded that immediate LC should become the treatment of choice for operable patients with acute cholecystitis. Kolla *et al* mentioned several key points that should be considered when performing laparoscopic cholecystectomy, which includes decompression of the gall bladder allowing better grasping and retraction. In our study decompression was required in 44.4% of the earlier group, whereas in the afore mentioned study decompression was required for 80% of the cases.¹⁵

Most surgeons agree that the timing of the procedure is an important factor in determining the outcome. Ideally the surgery should be performed within the “golden 72 hour” from the onset of symptoms has been suggested. Such early surgery is not always

possible because of logistic difficulty in performing surgery for such patients on emergency basis. Time is a critical factor in surgery of acute cholecystitis surgery.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ According to Zhu *et al*²⁰ Gallbladder inflammation during the first 72 hours of onset of symptoms may not involve structures within the triangle of Callot. Surgical dissection within this critical period therefore appears easiest due to the lack of organised adhesions. Cholecystectomy within this timeframe reduces the risk of injury to the structures within the Callots triangle. This can be seen in low rates of complication and conversions. The mean operating time was 64.32 min vs. 58.24 min in the delayed group, the difference in time was statistically significant (*p*-value). Study done by Agarwal²¹ reports mean operating time for early 69.4 min versus 66.4 min for delayed group whereas another prospective randomised trial by Verma²² duration of surgery was 65.78 min vs. 56.83mins in delayed group. Kolla *et al*¹⁵ showed that, the mean operating time was 104 min in the early group and 93 min in the delayed group.

The overall complication rate in early group was 23.3% vs. 36.7% in the delayed group. This difference was statistically not significant contrary to that reported by Johansson *et al*⁴ (18% vs. 8%) and Kolla *et al* (20% versus 15%). Study by Lai *et al*¹⁸ showed no difference in the complication rate between the two groups (9% versus 8%). However, it is comparable with the other two prospective controlled studies by Lo *et al*⁸ (29%) and Gonzalez-Rodriguez *et al*²³ (17.7%) had shown significantly higher complication in the delayed group than in the early group. There were no major complications. Only one case of bile duct injury in the delayed group which was due to the obscure, unclear Callots triangle anatomy and delay in timely conversion to open cholecystectomy which suggests that early

laparoscopic cholecystectomy is a safe procedure.

In our study the conversion rate was seen to be 15.5% in early vs. 14.4% in delayed group which can also be seen in recently published Agrawal *et al* study where the conversion rate was 16% in early, due to dense adhesions all around, unclear and obscured Callot's triangle anatomy. The conversion rates in most of the studies lie in acceptable range and are comparable to our study. Waiting for the inflamed gallbladder to cool down allows maturation of the surrounding inflammation and results in the organization of the adhesions, leading to scarring and contraction which makes the dissection more difficult.

There was significant difference in hospital stay between both the groups. The total hospital stay was significantly less for the early group than the delayed group in our study which is consistent with other studies, which has also been reported by many other studies. There is a socioeconomic advantage as well as prevention of recurrent attacks and the complications during the waiting period. The postoperative pain scores and analgesia requirements were similar in the two groups.

The strengths of our study are that quality of data collected was good owing to rigours applied to it. The weaknesses are a non-randomized design and lack of collection of data on many independent variables. However, the outcome results may be useful.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, early laparoscopic cholecystectomy is safe and feasible for acute cholecystitis and is associated with fewer intraoperative and postoperative complications much shorter hospital stay, quick recovery (earlier return to work), which offers a major economic benefit to the health care system especially in our country by significant reduction of postoperative hospitalization and treatment cost. We therefore suggest that laparoscopic cholecystectomy be performed within 72 hours of admission.

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